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ORTHOPEDIC STRUCTURES WITH SUPPORT ON IMPLANTS

Abstract

Today, a pressing problem for the population is the loss of a significant number of teeth, which most often occurs as a result of dental diseases such as caries and its complications, periodontitis, and injuries to the maxillofacial region. The increasing destruction of the dental system leads to tooth loss. In this case, the main function of the masticatory apparatus is impaired, as well as the speech function and aesthetic standards. Defects in the dental arches can lead to occlusion disorders with further development of temporomandibular joint disease. Many patients, especially young people, refuse removable dentures due to unsatisfactory fixation and stabilization of the structure, painful sensations when chewing, as well as due to the impact on the psychoemotional state [5]. For several decades, orthopedic structures with support on implants, which are implanted into the alveolar bone, have been popular among patients with partial or complete absence of teeth. This can be explained by the fact that this design creates the most accurate restoration of functions than other types of prosthetics[6].

Keywords: dental implants; partial edentia; complete edentia; osseointegration; fixed prosthetics; abutment

One of the main conditions of dental implantation is the correct planning of this procedure, which is the development of an optimal orthopedic treatment plan. As a result of planning, the prosthetic option, type, size and number of implants are determined. In addition, a step-by-step orthopedic and surgical treatment is drawn up. In dental implantation, it is important to note the phenomenon of osseointegration, which is the connection of the bone structures of the peri-implantation zone with the implant through the formation of a bone or bone-like substance on its surface without an intermediate connective tissue layer. This phenomenon includes 3 stages: Osteoconduction. Consists of the formation of the primary matrix on the implant surface. Direct bone formation, which is formed as a result of mineralization of the bone matrix. Secondary restructuring or remodeling. There are 2 methods of prosthetics on implants: direct. Fixation of a prefabricated prosthesis occurs directly on the operating table. Delayed prosthetics is performed a certain period after implantation. One-stage dental implantation is performed in the presence of a large gum attachment zone, a wide alveolar ridge, good oral hygiene, and a stable temporary prosthesis. Two-stage implantation is indicated for augmentation, low bone density, somatic diseases, periodontal risk factors, and low bone density. All implant-supported prosthesis designs are divided into 3 groups according to the principle of their fixation: fixed (fixed with cement), conditionally removable (screw fastening), and removable prostheses. If one tooth is missing, the best solution would be to make a single crown supported by an implant. If it is necessary to make a bridge prosthesis supported by teeth and implants, several teeth should be splinted, which reduces their physiological mobility and decreases the risk of overload. Implants used as an intermediate support for a bridge prosthesis with a large-scale defect in the dental arch reduce the risk of overload. There are several types of structures that can prevent implant overload. These include crushers and a load absorber. They are semi-la-

bile locking fasteners or detachable connecting elements with screw or lock fixation that unite parts of a fixed prosthesis and provide some mobility of one of the parts. The main disadvantage of manufacturing dental prostheses with crushers is the technical complexity, as well as the need for expensive equipment. A similar role can be played by the use of conditionally removable structures. A threaded connection, as a rule, leaves some mobility of a fixed prosthesis fixed to an implant. As a result, the risk of implant overload is compensated to a greater extent. When transmitting the chewing load along the implant axis, the pressure is distributed into the bone tissue and prevents alveolar ridge atrophy. Many implantologists recommend using temporary prostheses on implants to prepare the mucous membrane of the alveolar process around the future crown on the implant. A special place in dental implantation is occupied by the choice of material for orthopedic structures, on which the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment largely depends. The most common material for implantation is titanium (99.7%) and its alloy TiAl6V4 (90% Ti, 6% Al and 4% V). The great popularity of titanium is due to the formation of a strong integration between the surface of the titanium implant and the tissues surrounding it. In addition, titanium is not a noble metal, and its surface is covered with a biologically inert oxide film, due to which the decomposition of this material in vivo is minimal. The optimal design in implantology is considered to be a combined chewing surface of fixed dentures, where only the occlusal platforms are modeled from metal at the points of transfer of the vertical load to the implant. Due to this, the bite height is maintained and the "grinding" of the chewing surfaces of the dental arches is facilitated. Currently, orthopedic treatment with support on implants is the production of one-piece non-removable structures that can be faced with dental porcelain or plastic. The simplest designs of one-stage implants are non-separable, and when using them, the heads of the implants are prepared in the oral cavity, if necessary, just like human teeth, and the subsequent stages of

prosthetics are almost similar to the clinical and laboratory stages of the production of conventional one-piece cast or metal-ceramic (metal-plastic) structures.

Two-stage implants have a complex design and consist of several parts that are connected by a thread. Using a disassemblable model, a dental technician can select and mill the implant head (abutment) in full accordance with the clinical situation, creating the best most favorable conditions for modeling and fitting the covering structure. As a result, this ensures an accurate marginal fit of the crown, compared to prosthetics, in which natural teeth are the support. The manufacture of a fixed prosthesis consists of clinical and laboratory stages, which alternate with each other. The doctor obtains a preliminary impression using alginate materials. Next, a plaster model is made on which the boundaries of the individual spoon are outlined, after which it is made of plastic. In accordance with the type of impression transfer used, the technician maintains a gap in the projection of the implant. The extraction of the gingival cuff formers and fixation of impression analogs in the implants occurs on the day of obtaining the working impression. In a closed-tray impression, the impression analogue resembles a medium-height abutment, is fixed in the implant with a screw, and a plastic impression cap is tightly snapped onto it. Then the doctor takes an impression with a monophasic impression material. The resulting impression is sent to the dental laboratory. The dental technician fixes the laboratory analogues of the implants to the transfers and casts the working model. It is also necessary to make an "artificial gum" on the model when prosthetics with fixed dentures on implants. The "open spoon" technique is used in the manufacture of long-span bridge prostheses. It improves the quality of the impression and prevents displacement of the impression analogues. The spoon is perforated in the projection of the analogues so that they protrude into the hole. Then the monophasic material is introduced into the spoon and an impression is obtained. After the material has hardened, the doctor unscrews the screws that fix the impression analogues and removes the impression. In the laboratory, the dental technician attaches laboratory analogs of the implants to the impression analogs and casts a model with an artificial gum. On the same day, the doctor receives an auxiliary impression of the antagonists and determines the central relationship of the jaws. The dental technician casts the models, fixes them in the articulator, selects the abutments and mills them, if necessary. Then the abutments are fixed on the model, the framework of the cast prosthesis is modeled and sent for casting. The technician adjusts the cast framework to the models and sends it to the clinic for checking. Having assessed the accuracy of the frame fit to all implant heads and the correctness of the restoration of occlusal relationships on metal occlusal surfaces, the doctor again determines the central ratio of the jaws (with frames on the implants), the color of the facing material and the anatomical shape of the teeth of the prosthesis, after which he returns the models with the frames and all working notes to the laboratory. In the dental laboratory, the frame is finished and the facings are modeled

in accordance with the type of facing material, the relationship of the dental arches and the doctor's instructions. The finished prosthesis is adjusted in the oral cavity, special attention is paid to the accuracy of its fit to the implant heads and occlusal relationships in all phases of articulation. If the prosthesis meets all requirements, it is fixed with cement. Conditionally removable prosthetics is carried out when only implants are used as a support for the denture. In this case, the use of plate implants is contraindicated. Conditionally removable prostheses are usually called superstructures that are fixed to the implant heads using a threaded connection (screws). The prosthesis is fixed to the implant heads with screws, and the holes above them are closed with filling materials. The clinical and laboratory stages of manufacturing conditionally removable prostheses are generally similar to those in the manufacture of fixed prostheses, but have a number of features. In conditionally removable prosthetics, impressions are obtained in an open way. The screws are unscrewed and the spoon is removed from the patient's oral cavity. Laboratory analogues are fixed with screws and a working model is cast, on which the dental technician models the prosthesis frame. The thread for connecting the prosthesis body to the implant heads can be created with a screw in a wax blank or by using technical caps, which can be burnt out or metal and not burnt out. After modeling, the frame is cast, adjusted to the model and returned to the clinic. After trying on, the dental technician covers the frame with plastic or ceramics and hands it back to the doctor. The finished prosthesis is adjusted to the implant heads and fixed with screws. After that, the holes are closed with filling material.

Implant-supported dentures mostly have difficult access to the implant neck for hygiene procedures. Therefore, patients with such dentures are classified as people with insufficient oral care. In order to prevent trauma to the implant surface by metal during professional denture hygiene, it is necessary to use implacers, which are plastic or metal instruments with a Teflon-coated working part. It is also necessary to consider the issue of maintaining and restoring normal oral microbiocenosis, since this is an important factor in maintaining dental health. Conclusion. Thus, prosthetics using dental implants is an effective method of treating patients with included defects, limited healthy teeth, as well as terminal defects and complete edentia. Due to the uniform distribution of chewing pressure, chewing function is restored faster. Reliable fixation of the structure ensures the absence of discomfort when eating and talking, and improves the psychoemotional state of patients with partial and complete absence of teeth. The success of this type of orthopedic treatment depends on a combination of a number of external and internal factors, including: the choice of the optimal number, model and location of supporting implants, the configuration of the prosthetic superstructure, the technique of conducting the surgical and postoperative stages of treatment.

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